

Comparing Feature Selection Methods in Clinical Data Modeling: LASSO, Ridge, Elastic Net, SCAD, Boruta, Best Subset, and Stepwise Regression

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Abstract

Accurate variable selection is essential for predictive modeling in clinical research, yet guidance on method choice under varying data conditions is limited. We systematically evaluated stepwise regression, best subset selection, Boruta, and four regularization-based methods (LASSO, Ridge, Elastic Net, SCAD) using simulated datasets and a prospective study of endogenous hypercortisolism in patients with difficult-to-control type 2 diabetes. Key metrics included predictive performance, parameter estimation, and feature selection accuracy. Stepwise and best subset methods performed well in low-dimensional, low-collinearity settings, offering interpretable and parsimonious models without hyperparameter tuning. In medium-to-high dimensional or highly correlated settings, regularized methods yielded more stable and accurate predictions, while Boruta identified a complementary set of features overlooked by linear models.

These results provide practical guidance for choosing variable selection methods and suggest that combining complementary approaches can enhance both feature discovery and interpretability in clinical datasets.

Key Words: LASSO, stepwise regression, simulation, hypercortisolism.

1. Introduction

Feature selection is a critical step in clinical data modeling, yet there remains a lack of practical guidance on when to use specific methods. Each approach has its own strengths and limitations, making the choice highly context-dependent. Clinical datasets often present unique challenges: a large number of candidate predictors, many of which may be irrelevant or noisy; relatively small sample sizes due to the high cost of patient recruitment; and strong correlations among variables. These factors increase the risk of overfitting and poor generalizability if not properly addressed. Moreover, interpretability is essential in clinical research, which explains why linear regression remains widely used despite the availability of more complex modeling techniques. Taken together, these characteristics underscore the importance of robust feature selection strategies in building reliable and clinically meaningful models.

A commonly used classical approach for variable selection is stepwise regression, which iteratively adds or removes predictors based on information criteria or hypothesis tests. While stepwise methods have been widely applied in clinical research for their simplicity and interpretability, they are known to suffer from several limitations in high-dimensional settings. These include model instability, and a propensity to overfit, particularly when the number of features (p) is large relative to the sample size (n) (Derksen & Keselman, 1992; Harrell, 2015).

Another commonly used classical approach is best subset regression, which attempts to identify the combination of predictors that provides the best fit according to a criterion such as AIC, BIC, or adjusted R^2 . Unlike stepwise procedures, best subset regression conducts an exhaustive search

across all possible predictor combinations, which guarantees that the identified model is globally optimal under the chosen metric. The main advantages of this approach are its interpretability and transparency. However, it quickly becomes computationally prohibitive as the number of predictors grows, and like stepwise regression, it is prone to instability and overfitting in small-sample, high-dimensional settings (Miller, 2002).

To address these challenges, regularization methods have emerged as powerful alternatives by imposing penalties on model complexity. The Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) (Tibshirani, 1996) applies an L1 penalty, encouraging sparsity by shrinking some coefficients exactly to zero and thereby performing variable selection. Ridge regression (Hoerl & Kennard, 1970), which uses an L2 penalty, shrinks coefficients toward zero but retains all predictors, offering improved stability when predictors are highly correlated, as correlated features tend to shrink together. The Elastic Net (Zou & Hastie, 2005) combines L1 and L2 penalties, providing a balance between sparsity and stability, and is particularly effective when groups of correlated features are present. In addition, nonconvex penalties such as the Smoothly Clipped Absolute Deviation (SCAD) (Fan & Li, 2001) have been proposed to overcome the estimation bias introduced by LASSO, especially for predictors with large true effects, while still producing sparse and interpretable models.

Beyond regression-based methods, feature selection approaches leveraging tree-based models have gained popularity in clinical and biomedical research. Methods such as Boruta (Kursa & Rudnicki, 2010) build upon Random Forests to assess the importance of each variable in predicting the outcome. Boruta iteratively compares the importance of real features to that of permuted features, selecting only those that consistently show stronger predictive power. The advantage of tree-based approaches lies in their ability to naturally capture nonlinearities and interactions among predictors, without the need for strong modeling assumptions. However, they often sacrifice interpretability compared to linear models.

Taken together, these diverse methods highlight the trade-offs between interpretability, stability, and predictive performance that are central to feature selection in clinical data modeling. Despite the wide array of available approaches, there remains limited practical guidance for clinical researchers on when to use which method. This study aims to fill that gap by systematically comparing stepwise regression, best subset regression, LASSO, Ridge, Elastic Net, SCAD, and Boruta, using both simulated data and real clinical datasets.

1.1 Stepwise Regression via F-Test-Based Feature Selection

Variable selection in stepwise regression is based on null hypothesis testing, most commonly through the F-test. In forward selection, the procedure begins with an empty model (or only the intercept). At each step t , the improvement in model fit from adding a candidate predictor is assessed using the partial F-statistic. The predictor with the smallest p -value is added, provided it falls below a prespecified inclusion threshold α . A larger α increases the likelihood of including more predictors but also raises the false positive rate. In contrast, backward elimination starts with the full model and sequentially removes the predictor with the largest p -value, continuing until no variable exceeds the elimination threshold. The bidirectional (stepwise) procedure combines both approaches, allowing variables to be added or removed at each step, so that predictors previously included can later be excluded. The algorithm terminates once no further predictors meet the entry or removal criteria, yielding a final model determined by sequential hypothesis testing.

1.2 Best subset regression

In best subset regression, the goal is to identify the model of size $k \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ that minimizes a chosen selection criterion, such as AIC, BIC, Mallows' C_p , or adjusted R^2 . A naïve implementation requires fitting all 2^p possible models, which is computationally infeasible when p is large. To address this, the “leaps and bounds” algorithm (Furnival & Wilson, 1974) was developed, which

prunes the search space by discarding subsets that cannot possibly improve the criterion value. This approach substantially reduces the computational burden while still guaranteeing that the optimal subset is identified for each model size. Practical implementations are widely available, including the leaps package in R for linear regression, and the glmulti package, which generalizes best subset selection to generalized linear models such as logistic regression (Calcagno & de Mazancourt, 2010). Despite its advantages in terms of interpretability and optimality under the chosen criterion, best subset regression can remain computationally demanding in moderate-to-high dimensions and is sensitive to collinearity among predictors.

1.3 LASSO

LASSO adds an ℓ_1 penalty to the ordinary least squares (OLS) objective:

$$\hat{\beta} = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i^T \beta)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| \right\}$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ is a tuning parameter that controls the strength of regularization. The ℓ_1 penalty encourages sparsity, shrinking some coefficients exactly to zero, thereby performing variable selection. As λ increases, more coefficients are shrunk to zero, yielding simpler models; when $\lambda=0$, the solution reduces to ordinary least squares. In practice, λ is typically chosen via K -fold cross-validation, minimizing prediction error on held-out folds. Efficient algorithms make LASSO computationally feasible even when $p \gg n$, which has contributed to its widespread use in clinical applications.

1.4 Ridge

Ridge regression uses an ℓ_2 penalty instead:

$$\hat{\beta} = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i^T \beta)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p \rho_j^2 \right\}$$

Unlike LASSO, Ridge does not produce sparse models. All coefficients are shrunk toward zero but remain nonzero. This is beneficial when all variables contribute meaningfully to the outcome, such as in medical diagnosis models where biomarkers collectively improve disease prediction. However, it does not perform variable selection in the strict sense.

1.5 Elastic Net

Elastic Net combines the strengths of LASSO and Ridge by incorporating both ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 penalties:

$$\hat{\beta} = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i^T \beta)^2 + \lambda \left[\alpha \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| + (1 - \alpha) \sum_{j=1}^p \rho_j^2 \right] \right\}$$

where $\alpha \in [0,1]$ controls the mixing between LASSO ($\alpha=1$) and Ridge ($\alpha=0$). The dual regularization provides a flexible compromise between sparsity and stability. Tuning involves selecting both λ and α , usually via a two-dimensional grid search with cross-validation.

1.6 SCAD

The Smoothly Clipped Absolute Deviation (SCAD) penalty was designed to overcome the bias of LASSO for large coefficients while still yielding sparse solutions. The SCAD penalty is defined by a piecewise function that behaves like LASSO near zero (encouraging sparsity), but flattens out for larger coefficients, thereby providing unbiased estimates for large coefficients. The SCAD estimator solves:

$$\hat{\beta} = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - x_i^T \beta)^2 + \sum_{j=1}^p p_{\lambda}(|\beta_j|) \right\}$$

where $p_{\lambda}(\cdot)$ is the SCAD penalty function depending on λ and a tuning parameter a (commonly set to 3.7). Compared to LASSO and Ridge, SCAD's nonconvexity makes the optimization more challenging than for convex penalties.

1.7 Boruta algorithm

The Boruta algorithm (Kursa & Rudnicki, 2010) is a wrapper method built around Random Forests to perform all-relevant feature selection. Unlike LASSO, Ridge, or SCAD, which impose penalties in regression models, Boruta leverages the variable importance measure from Random Forests. At each iteration, a Random Forest model is fitted, and the importance score of each real feature is compared against the maximum importance among the permuted features (shadows). Features consistently outperforming the shadows are deemed “confirmed”, while those consistently underperforming are “rejected”. Features with intermediate performance are left “tentative”. The main advantage of Boruta is its ability to detect weak but relevant features, though at the cost of higher computational burden compared to single-model methods.

To summarize, the methods discussed above differ in their underlying selection mechanisms, computational efficiency, and behavior under multicollinearity or high-dimensional settings. **Table 1** provides a side-by-side comparison of these seven approaches, highlighting their key features, advantages, and limitations.

Table 1: Comparison of key features of the selected methods

Method	Type	Feature Selection Approach	Multicollinearity	Interpretability	Scalability
Stepwise Regression	Linear (GLM)	Greedy (Both directions)	Poorly	High	Moderate
Best Subset	Linear (GLM)	Exhaustive Search	Poorly	High	Slow
LASSO	Linear (GLM)	Shrinkage (L1 penalty)	Good	High	Good
Ridge	Linear (GLM)	Shrinkage (L2 penalty)	Good	High	Good
Elastic Net	Linear (GLM)	Shrinkage (L1 + L2 penalty)	Good	High	Good
SCAD	Linear (GLM)	Shrinkage (Non-convex penalty)	Good	High	Moderate
Boruta	Tree-based	Importance from Random Forest	Generally robust	Moderate	Moderate

In this paper, we compare stepwise regression, best subset, LASSO, ridge regression, elastic net, and Boruta across both simulated datasets and real-world clinical data. Our evaluation focuses on predictive performance, parameter estimates, and feature selection accuracy under varying levels of sample size, predictor dimensionality, signal-to-noise ratio, sparsity, and collinearity. The remainder of the article is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present a simulation study designed to systematically compare the performance of these methods across controlled scenarios. Section 3 applies the methods to an empirical study aimed at identifying risk factors for hypercortisolism, illustrating their practical differences in a real clinical context. We conclude in Section 4 with a discussion of key findings and practical considerations for applying these techniques in clinical research.

2. Simulation Study

2.1 Simulation Design

To systematically assess model performance under diverse clinical data scenarios, we conducted a comprehensive simulation study based on a five-factor factorial design. The parameters were selected to mimic a wide range of conditions commonly encountered in clinical research. Specifically, we varied the following factors:

1. Sample size (N): Values of 100, 500, and 1000 were considered to represent small, medium, and large study sizes typical of clinical settings.
2. Number of candidate predictors (p): We examined predictor sets of size 15, 30, 50, 100, and 1000, spanning low-, moderate-, and high-dimensional settings.
3. Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR): let's denote the model as:

$$\mathbf{y}_0 = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_0) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0$$

where $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbf{R}^p$ is the independent variable and $\mathbf{y}_0 \in \mathbf{R}$ is the response variable. Then, the SNR is defined as:

$$SNR = \frac{\text{var}(\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_0))}{\text{var}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0)}$$

SNR values ranged from 0.05 to 4.5, corresponding to 2–80% of variance explained, with $SNR = 1$ representing 50% explained variance.

4. Sparsity level: Sparsity was defined as the proportion of truly nonzero coefficients in the underlying model. To approximate realistic conditions, five predictors were assigned coefficients of 1, while the remaining coefficients decayed exponentially toward zero:

$$\beta_{0i} = 0.5^{i-s}, \text{ for } i=6, \dots, p.$$

A threshold of $1e^{-2}$ distinguished true coefficients from negligible ones. By varying the total number of predictors, this setup captured differing assumptions about the number of relevant features.

5. Collinearity level: Predictors were generated from a multivariate normal distribution with first order autoregressive correlation structures. Correlation values of 0.2, 0.5, and 0.8 were used to represent weak, moderate, and strong collinearity, respectively.

Each simulation scenario was replicated 50 times to estimate the mean and standard deviation of each evaluation metric. For each replication, we generated both a training set and a test set of equal size under the same parameter configurations. The training set was used for model fitting, while the test set served to evaluate predictive accuracy, as described below.

2.2 Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate and compare the performance of each regression method across the simulated scenarios, we considered three aspects: predictive performance, parameter estimates and variable selection accuracy. These metrics were chosen to reflect the utility of the fitted model for prediction, the estimated coefficient values, and its ability to recover the true underlying structure of the data.

- Predictive performance was measured using the normalized root mean squared error (*NRMSE*) on an independent test set:

$$NRMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{test} * sd(y_i)} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{test}} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}$$

where y_i are the observed responses, \hat{y}_i is the predicted responses, $sd(y_i)$ is the standard deviation of the outcome in the test set, and n_{test} is the number of observations in the test set. Normalization by outcome variability allows comparability across scenarios.

- Parameter estimates were assessed by relative test error (*RTE*) (Hastie, Tibshirani, & Tibshirani, 2017), which measures the expected test error relative to the Bayes error rate:

$$\begin{aligned} RTE(\hat{\beta}) &= \frac{\mathbf{E}(y_0 - x_0^T \hat{\beta})^2}{\sigma^2} \\ &= \frac{(\hat{\beta} - \beta_0)^T \Sigma(\hat{\beta} - \beta_0) + \sigma^2}{\sigma^2} \end{aligned}$$

A perfect score of 1 indicates that the model exactly recovers the true coefficients, whereas the null score is given by $\frac{\beta_0^T \Sigma \beta_0 + \sigma^2}{\sigma^2} = SNR + 1$.

- Variable selection accuracy was evaluated by comparing the estimated support set (nonzero coefficients) against the ground truth. We computed the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (*MCC*) (Matthews, 1975), which provides a balanced summary of all four classification outcomes (*TP*, *TN*, *FP*, *FN*):

$$MCC = \frac{TP * TN - FP * FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}}$$

TP (true positives) are correctly selected nonzero coefficients, *TN* (true negatives) are correctly excluded zero coefficients, *FP* (false positives) are zero coefficients incorrectly selected, and *FN* (false negatives) are nonzero coefficients missed. The MCC ranges from -1 (complete disagreement) to 1 (perfect agreement), with 0 indicating random performance.

- Positive variable selection accuracy was quantified using the *F1* score (van Rijsbergen, 1979), which balances sensitivity and precision in identifying true predictors:

$$F1 = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall},$$

$$\text{where } Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \text{ and } Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

A key limitation of $F1$ score is its bias toward larger models: adding more variables typically increases recall (reducing false negatives) and thus inflates $F1$, even if many irrelevant predictors are included. To address this, we applied an adjusted $F1$ score that directly penalizes model size:

$$\text{Adjusted } F1 = F1 * \left(1 - \frac{\text{Number of features selected}}{\text{Number of features}}\right)$$

This adjustment reduces scores for unnecessarily large models, providing a fairer comparison across methods with different levels of sparsity.

2.3 Parameter tuning

Stepwise regression was performed with a p -value cutoff of 0.10 for variable entry and 0.05 for retention. For the best subset regression model, the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) was used to determine the optimal model size.

All cross-validation procedures were conducted using 10-fold cross-validation. The LASSO was tuned using cross-validation to select the penalty parameter λ . Two versions of the LASSO model were considered: one using λ_{min} , the value that minimizes the cross-validated prediction error, and another using λ_{1se} , the largest value of λ within one standard error of the minimum. These are referred to as LASSO (min) and LASSO (1se), respectively, in the following sections. Ridge regression was tuned in a similar manner, with λ selected according to the λ_{1se} rule. Elastic net regression was fit with equal weighting of the $\ell1$ and $\ell2$ penalties ($\alpha=0.5$), and λ tuning was performed following the λ_{1se} rule. For SCAD, the concavity parameter a was set to the commonly used default value of 3.7, and λ was chosen as λ_{min} .

In the Boruta procedure, only features confirmed as important were retained as selected predictors. The final random forest model was then built and tuned through a grid search over five candidate values of the number of predictors considered at each split, with cross-validation used to select the optimal configuration.

For stepwise regression and best subset selection, computational burden increased substantially as the feature space grew. To address this, we implemented predictor prefiltering based on the marginal correlation between each predictor and the response. Specifically, when the number of predictors was ≥ 1000 , stepwise regression was restricted to the top 100 features. For best subset selection, when the number of predictors was ≥ 100 , the analysis was restricted to the top 50 features.

2.4 Simulation Study Results

2.4.1 Predictive Performance

Predictive performance was evaluated using normalized RMSE, with results summarized in **Figure 1**. Each bar represents a method, where scenarios with $p < 100$ are considered low-dimensional and those with $SNR < 0.5$ are considered low-signal settings. Dots indicate model size, mapped to the secondary y-axis on the right. Model size for Ridge regression is not shown, since all coefficients remain nonzero and its model size is equal to the full feature space.

As expected, performance improved with higher SNR across all methods, yielding smaller RMSE values. In low-dimensional settings (small number of predictors), differences between stepwise regression, best subset, and regularization-based methods were minimal, and became negligible as sample size increased. Neither SNR level nor predictor correlation substantially altered this pattern. For LASSO, we compared two tuning strategies: λ_{min} which minimizes cross-validation error and results in larger models, and λ_{1se} , which applies stronger regularization and produces more

parsimonious models. In most cases, λ_{min} achieved better predictive accuracy, while λ_{1se} remained smaller in size, offering a trade-off between accuracy and parsimony.

In high-dimensional settings, the picture was markedly different. Regularization methods substantially outperformed stepwise and best subset approaches, particularly when sample size was small. These performance gaps diminished as sample size increased. Ridge regression, however, exhibited notable overfitting when SNR was high, since it shrinks coefficients but does not eliminate irrelevant predictors, leading to inflated prediction error.

Tree-based models displayed distinct behavior. Random forests performed comparably well under low SNR, but under high SNR they underperformed relative to stepwise regression. This suggests that their inherent bias, resulting from bagging and random splits, can hinder performance when the underlying signal is purely linear. Interestingly, predictor collinearity improved the predictive accuracy of random forests: when multiple correlated predictors carried the true signal, the probability of capturing it at a split increased, thereby enhancing model performance.

Overall, regularization-based methods showed the most stable predictive performance across simulation scenarios, particularly in high-dimensional settings. While SNR had little impact on the relative ranking of methods, collinearity modestly benefited tree-based approaches. These results suggest that regularization methods are generally preferable for clinical datasets with many predictors, whereas stepwise regression and best subset remain attractive options in settings with large samples and small feature spaces, as they require no hyperparameter tuning.

Figure 1

Figure 1. Predictive performance measured by normalized RMSE across simulation settings. Bars represent methods, with low-dimensional settings defined as $p < 100$ and low-SNR settings as $\text{SNR} < 0.5$. Dots indicate model size (right y-axis).

2.4.2 Parameter Estimates

Parameter estimates were evaluated using relative test error, which quantifies how closely the estimated regression coefficients align with the true coefficients. A score of 1 indicates perfect recovery of the true coefficients, and lower scores reflect smaller estimation error. **Figure 2** summarizes the results, with the dotted black curve representing the null model. Boruta is excluded from this metric because tree-based methods do not yield explicit coefficient estimates.

The relative test error patterns are primarily determined by the sample size-to-predictor ratio.

When $p = 15$ (**Figure 2a**), methods cluster into three groups. The first group is LASSO (min), which consistently achieves the lowest relative test error across conditions. The second group includes stepwise regression, best subset, and SCAD. These methods perform well when correlation is low and SNR is high, but their performance worsens as predictor correlation increases. The third group is LASSO (1se), Ridge, and Elastic Net. These methods perform reasonably when SNR is low but deteriorate sharply as SNR increases, making them the least accurate in this setting. As sample size increases, the performance of the first and second groups converges, while the third group remains suboptimal. The difference between LASSO (min) and LASSO (1se) highlights the critical role of tuning regularization parameters. Although the curves appear well separated in **Figure 2a**, the actual differences are modest, on the order of 0.05 on the y-axis.

When $p = 50$ (**Figure 2b**), stepwise regression and best subset are the worst-performing methods at small sample sizes such as $N = 100$. With larger sample sizes, their accuracy improves and approaches that of LASSO (min). At the same time, Elastic Net, Ridge, and LASSO (1se) appear relatively worse as N grows. The overall pattern resembles the case with $p = 15$, except that stepwise regression and best subset never fully reach the accuracy of LASSO (min). The case with $p = 30$ exhibits a pattern similar to that observed for $p = 50$ and is therefore not shown.

When $p = 1000$ (**Figures 2c-d**), Ridge regression dominates the plot with very high relative test errors, compressing the lines of other methods. After removing Ridge from the display, it becomes clear that stepwise regression and best subset perform poorly in high dimensions, although their accuracy improves toward that of the regularized methods as SNR and sample size increase. Overall relative test error decreases with larger sample sizes, showing that sufficient data can offset the challenges of high dimensionality. Across these scenarios, LASSO (min) and SCAD provide the most accurate coefficient estimates. SCAD performs best when correlation is low, whereas LASSO (min) excels when correlation is high. The case with $p = 100$ exhibits a similar pattern to $p = 1000$.

In summary, model accuracy is primarily determined by the sample size to predictor ratio. High SNR improves the performance of stepwise regression and best subset but has limited benefit for regularized methods. Predictor correlation destabilizes stepwise regression and best subset while leaving regularization-based approaches relatively unaffected. LASSO (min) consistently produces the most accurate coefficient estimates, although in settings with large sample size relative to the number of predictors, stepwise regression and best subset achieve similar accuracy without requiring hyperparameter tuning.

Figure 2

Figure 2. Relative test error of coefficient estimates across simulation settings. The dotted black line denotes the null model. Higher scores indicate greater accuracy. Ridge regression inflates error in high-dimensional settings ($p=1000$), so separate plots are provided.

2.4.3 Variable Selection Accuracy

Variable selection accuracy was assessed using the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), which provides a balanced measure of performance by incorporating all four classification outcomes (true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives). MCC is particularly valuable in this setting because feature selection is highly imbalanced, with only a small fraction of predictors being truly relevant. Ridge regression was excluded from this comparison since it does not shrink coefficients to zero and therefore cannot produce a sparse support set.

Figure 3 presents a heatmap of the scaled MCC of all 7 methods scores under each simulation setting. Because SNR levels did not impact too much the relative ranking of methods, we averaged MCC across SNR values. In the heatmap, red indicates relatively poor performance, green indicates strong performance, and white reflects results near the median performance.

Collinearity exerted a major influence on MCC. At low correlation ($\rho = 0.2$), LASSO (1se) and Elastic Net achieved the highest MCC scores. Boruta gradually caught up to these methods as sample size increased beyond 500, reflecting its strength when more data are available to stabilize feature importance rankings. Best subset performed reasonably well at moderate-to-large sample sizes, while stepwise regression showed acceptable accuracy only when both the sample size was at

least 500 and the feature space was small ($p = 15$ or 30). The weakest performers in this setting were LASSO (min) and SCAD. The underperformance of LASSO (min) reflects its tendency to select overly large models, which reduces specificity by including many irrelevant predictors. SCAD, similarly, applies a less aggressive penalty than LASSO (1se). Although this design reduces bias for large coefficients, it also makes SCAD more prone to retaining borderline predictors. As a result, both methods exhibit higher false positive rates, resulting in lower MCC scores.

When correlation increased to $\rho = 0.5$, the accuracy of stepwise regression and best subset declined noticeably. At this level, Boruta began to outperform most competitors, owing to the fact that random forests can exploit redundancy among correlated features to stabilize variable importance estimates. At high correlation ($\rho = 0.8$), Boruta's advantage became even more pronounced. In contrast, stepwise regression and best subset became highly unstable because collinearity makes variable entry and removal decisions sensitive to small perturbations in the data, leading to inconsistent selections and reduced accuracy.

In summary, variable selection accuracy was strongly shaped by correlation, sample size, and feature size. LASSO (1se) and Elastic Net were the most reliable in low-correlation settings, while Boruta excelled under higher correlation and larger samples. Stepwise and best subset methods were highly sensitive to collinearity, and LASSO (min) tended to over-select features, underscoring the trade-off between predictive power and selection accuracy. This highlights an important distinction: methods that optimize predictive accuracy are not always the best at producing parsimonious and accurate feature subsets.

Figure 3. Heatmap of scaled Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) scores across simulation settings, averaged over SNR levels. Green indicates higher accuracy; red indicates lower accuracy. Ridge regression is excluded since it does not yield sparse models.

To further investigate this trade-off, we next evaluate variable selection using the F1 score, which balances precision and recall. While MCC emphasizes overall agreement between true and selected features, the F1 score highlights the balance between capturing true signals and avoiding false discoveries. Together, these two metrics provide complementary perspectives on selection accuracy.

Because the F1 score focuses only on the positive class, it is inherently influenced by model size: larger models tend to yield higher recall, and thus higher F1, even if they include many irrelevant predictors. To account for this, **Figure 4** presents adjusted F1 scores that incorporate a penalty for excessive model size. Patterns across different sample sizes were similar, so we display results for $N = 500$ as a representative case.

At low dimensionality and low correlation, best subset selection performs reasonably well, often surpassing stepwise regression. However, both methods deteriorate under high-dimensional or highly correlated settings, reflecting their instability when predictor space is complex. In contrast, Boruta achieves the highest or near-highest *F1* scores across most scenarios. An exception occurs when the number of predictors is small ($p = 15$) and correlation is high ($\rho = 0.8$), where Boruta constructs disproportionately large models compared with other methods. This likely reflects the behavior of random forests under strong correlation: correlated predictors reinforce each other's importance scores, causing Boruta to retain many redundant features. The inflated model size leads to a lower adjusted F1 score in this setting, despite strong raw signal capture.

Across scenarios, Elastic Net and LASSO (1se) consistently emerge as the next-best performers, benefiting from stronger regularization that balances sensitivity and specificity. In contrast, LASSO (min) and SCAD typically show the weakest F1 performance. Both methods tend to select larger models with many borderline predictors, yielding higher recall but poor precision and therefore lower adjusted F1.

In summary, F1 results highlight that stronger regularization produces more parsimonious and accurate variable sets, while weakly penalized methods trade off precision for recall. Overall, Boruta strike the best balance between stability, parsimony, and sensitivity, complementing the insights gained from MCC. Among linear models, Elastic Net and LASSO (1se) represent the most effective choices.

Figure 4

Figure 4. Adjusted F1 scores across simulation settings ($N = 500$). Columns represent different numbers of predictors, and rows represent different levels of predictor correlation.

Our simulation results reveal that data features—sample size, feature number, collinearity, sparsity level and pattern, and SNR—had a substantial impact on model performance. To provide practical guidance: (1) when feature size is small with low collinearity, stepwise and best subset deliver good predictive performance and variable selection accuracy, offering balanced model size without requiring hyperparameter tuning; (2) when feature size is medium to large, or when collinearity is high, regularized methods generally provide more stable predictive performance, and Boruta achieves the strongest feature selection accuracy; (3) methods that maximize predictive accuracy do not necessarily yield the most accurate feature selection.

In summary, no single method dominates across all conditions. LASSO (1se) and Elastic Net provide the most reliable linear approaches, balancing predictive accuracy and selection stability, while Boruta offers a competitive and often superior alternative in correlated settings. Stepwise and best subset remain viable only in low-dimensional, low-correlation scenarios. Methods with weaker regularization tended to over-select features, underscoring the risk of conflating predictive accuracy with variable selection accuracy. Together, these findings clarify the strengths and limitations of widely used selection strategies and provide guidance for choosing appropriate methods under varying data conditions.

3. Empirical Study

3.1 Multicenter study of hypercortisolism in patients with difficult-to-control type 2 diabetes (CATALYST)

Type 2 diabetes (T2D) is a complex metabolic disorder frequently complicated by insulin resistance and heightened cardiovascular risk. While most patients respond to optimized standard-of-care (SOC) therapies, physicians are faced with finding treatment solutions for patients who do not respond adequately and have difficulty to control T2D. Emerging evidence suggests that unrecognized hypercortisolism may underlie poor glycemic control and related complications, yet its prevalence and clinical impact in this population remain poorly understood.

The CATALYST study was a multicenter Phase 4 trial designed to address this gap. Our work focuses on Part 1, the observational screening phase, which assessed the prevalence of hypercortisolism among patients with uncontrolled T2D despite receiving SOC therapy. Hypercortisolism was defined by post-dexamethasone suppression test (DST) cortisol >1.8 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ with dexamethasone level ≥ 140 ng/dL . Results (Buse et al., 2025) showed that approximately 24% of such patients had hypercortisolism, and stepwise regression was used to explore associated clinical characteristics.

In our analysis, we revisit this dataset by applying a range of classic and modern feature selection methods, comparing their performance with the published stepwise analysis results and evaluating whether alternative approaches yield consistent or divergent insights. Together with our simulation study, this empirical analysis provides a real-world assessment of the strengths and limitations of different modeling strategies.

3.2 Empirical Study Data

This analysis was conducted using data from 1,057 participants enrolled in the CATALYST study. Among these participants, 252 (24%) were identified as having hypercortisolism based on a 1-mg DST, while 805 did not meet the criteria. The dataset comprised 30 baseline features encompassing demographic variables and prior medication use (**Table 2**, stratified by hypercortisolism status). These features were selected by expert physicians for their clinical relevance and established links to disease mechanisms. Predictor correlations were centered near zero (median 0.04), with a maximum correlation of 0.86. The analytical objectives were twofold: (1) to identify clinical characteristics associated with hypercortisolism using different feature selection methods, and (2) to assess the stability and predictive performance of the selected features across methods.

Table 2: Baseline Features			
Feature	All Patients (N=1057)	Hypercortisolism (N=252)	No hypercortisolism (N=805)
Age (years)	60.7 (10.4)	63.8 (9.6)	59.8 (10.5)
Baseline Height (cm)	169.5 (10.8)	171.6 (10.9)	168.8 (10.7)
Number of Antihyperglycemic Medication Classes	3.4 (1.0)	3.6 (1.0)	3.4 (1.0)
Number of Antihypertensive Medication Classes	1.6 (1.1)	2.0 (1.2)	1.5 (1.1)
Region			
Mid West	128 (12.1%)	47 (18.7%)	81 (10.1%)
South West	480 (45.4%)	87 (34.5%)	393 (48.8%)
Other	449 (42.5%)	118 (46.8%)	331 (41.1%)
Race			
White	748 (70.8%)	187 (74.2%)	561 (69.7%)
Non-White	309 (29.2%)	65 (25.8%)	244 (30.3%)
Ethnicity			
Hispanic or Latino	255 (24.1%)	21 (8.3%)	234 (29.1%)
Non-Hispanic/Latino	802 (75.9%)	231 (91.7%)	571 (70.9%)
Baseline BMI Group			
<30	352 (33.3%)	93 (36.9%)	259 (32.2%)
≥30	705 (66.7%)	159 (63.1%)	546 (67.8%)
Metformin	783 (74.1%)	176 (69.8%)	607 (75.4%)
Pioglitazone	120 (11.4%)	35 (13.9%)	85 (10.6%)
SGLT2 Inhibitors	551 (52.1%)	157 (62.3%)	394 (48.9%)
Tirzepatide	110 (10.4%)	37 (14.7%)	73 (9.1%)
Any Antihypertensive Medications	866 (81.9%)	226 (89.7%)	640 (79.5%)
Diuretics	331 (31.3%)	111 (44%)	220 (27.3%)
Beta Blocking Agents	334 (31.6%)	114 (45.2%)	220 (27.3%)
Calcium Channel Blockers	261 (24.7%)	83 (32.9%)	178 (22.1%)
Lipid Modifying Agents	880 (83.3%)	226 (89.7%)	654 (81.2%)
Statins	830 (78.5%)	210 (83.3%)	620 (77%)
Fibrates	83 (7.9%)	36 (14.3%)	47 (5.8%)
Other Cardiovascular Medications	90 (8.5%)	33 (13.1%)	57 (7.1%)
Analgesics	321 (30.4%)	95 (37.7%)	226 (28.1%)
Opioids	65 (6.1%)	22 (8.7%)	43 (5.3%)
Psychiatric Medications	312 (29.5%)	94 (37.3%)	218 (27.1%)
Psycholeptics	141 (13.3%)	42 (16.7%)	99 (12.3%)
Psychoanaleptics	251 (23.7%)	75 (29.8%)	176 (21.9%)
Insulin and SGLT2 inhibitor	375 (35.5%)	106 (42.1%)	269 (33.4%)
GLP-1 receptor agonist and SGLT2 inhibitor	295 (27.9%)	88 (34.9%)	207 (25.7%)
Insulin and GLP-1 receptor agonist and SGLT2 inhibitor	197 (18.6%)	58 (23%)	139 (17.3%)
Took Maximum Dose of Any GLP-1 receptor agonist	197 (18.6%)	59 (23.4%)	138 (17.1%)
≥100 U Total Insulin	110 (10.4%)	34 (13.5%)	76 (9.4%)

Data are means (SD) for numeric variables, and count (percentage) for categorical variables.

3.3 Empirical Study Results

In the empirical study, Patients were randomly split into 80% training and 20% test sets, repeated 1,000 times. Training sets were used for feature selection and model development, while test sets were used to evaluate predictive performance. Results were summarized across all replicates.

Predictive performance was evaluated using test-set AUC. **Figure 5** presents the distribution of AUC values across 1,000 replicates for each method. LASSO (min) and Ridge achieved the highest AUCs, with Ridge showing a slight numerical advantage. Stepwise regression and SCAD followed closely. However, model size differed substantially: the median number of features was 22 for LASSO (min) compared with 8 for stepwise regression, despite minimal differences in median AUC (0.69 vs. 0.70). Taken together, these results suggest that stepwise regression offers the most favorable balance between predictive performance and parsimony in this setting.

Figure 5

Figure 5. Distribution of test-set AUC and model size across 1,000 replicates for each method. (a) AUC, (b) Model size.

When it comes to feature selection, four predictors were consistently selected across all models: the number of antihypertensive medication classes, non-Latino/Hispanic ethnicity, age, and prior use of fibrates. Stepwise regression analysis from Buse et al. (2025) showed a one-unit increase in the number of antihypertensive medication classes was associated with a 1.4-fold higher risk of hypercortisolism; Non-Latino/Hispanic ethnicity was associated with a 3.7-fold higher risk; each 10-year increase in age corresponded to a 1.3-fold higher risk; and prior fibrate use was linked to a 2.7-fold higher risk. The consistency of these features across diverse methods highlights their importance and suggests they are strong candidates for further validation.

Figure 6

Figure 6. Heatmap of feature selection across methods. Each row represents a feature and each column a method. Methods are ordered by hierarchical clustering.

Figure 6 presents the feature selection heatmap, where each row represents a feature and each column a method, with methods ordered by hierarchical clustering. Four feature clusters, outlined by black boxes, highlight groups of methods with similar selection patterns. LASSO (min) and SCAD produced the largest models, reflecting weaker regularization, whereas LASSO (1se) and Elastic Net selected more similar and parsimonious sets of features under stronger regularization. Stepwise regression and best subset identified largely overlapping features, with stepwise regression selecting more. Boruta, which performed best in simulation studies, displayed the most distinct selection pattern. To explore these differences in detail, **Table 3** contrasts features selected by stepwise regression (Buse et al., 2025) versus Boruta. Stepwise regression uniquely identified prior use of SGLT2 inhibitors, analgesics, tirzepatide, maximum dose of GLP-1 receptor agonists, and BMI, features primarily related to hyperglycemia. In contrast, Boruta uniquely selected prior use of diuretics and beta-blockers, features more reflective of hypertension. Given the strong correlation between hyperglycemia- and hypertension-related variables, these differences suggest that distinct modeling approaches may emphasize different aspects of patient clinical profiles. Stepwise regression provides a more straightforward interpretation, as hyperglycemia is directly linked to poorly controlled diabetes, but Boruta raises the possibility that hypertension-related factors may also play an important role in this population.

Table 3. Features Selected by Stepwise Regression Compared with Boruta Analysis

Feature selected by Stepwise regression (Buse et al., 2025)	Feature selected by Boruta	Times selected in 1000 replicates
	Ethnicity = Hispanic/Latino	1000
	Number of Antihypertensive Classes	999
	Age	807
	Fibrates	846
	Diuretics	988
	Region	909
	Beta Blocking Agents	595

SGLT2 inhibitor		471
Analgesics		203
Tirzepatide		171
BMI \geq 30		34
Took Maximum Dose of Any GLP-1		3

To better visualize frequently selected features (defined as appearing in at least 50% of replicates) across methods, an UpSet plot was generated (**Figure 7**). The LASSO (min) model produced the largest set, more than twice as large as the other methods, with 5 unique features and 5 features shared only with SCAD. As noted earlier, four features were consistently identified by all methods. Best subset yielded the most parsimonious model, selecting only these four features, while LASSO (1se) added one additional predictor (SGLT2 inhibitor). Boruta, stepwise regression, and Elastic Net produced models of comparable size, largely selecting subsets of LASSO (min) features. Overall, there was substantial overlap in selected features, though the relative importance ranking varied across methods.

Figure 7

Figure 7. UpSet plot of features selected $\geq 50\%$ of the time across different methods.

In summary, the real-data analyses reinforce our simulation findings: while multiple methods achieve strong predictive performance, they differ in the balance between parsimony and stability. Stepwise regression provides interpretable, compact models without the need for hyperparameter tuning and proves to be a practical and effective option in this setting. Meanwhile, Boruta identifies complementary signals that may capture alternative clinical pathways, offering additional insights beyond those of traditional linear approaches.

4. Discussion

In this study, we systematically evaluated the performance of stepwise regression, best subset, Boruta, and four regularization-based methods, LASSO, Ridge, SCAD and Elastic Net, across simulated scenarios and real-world clinical data from the CATALYST study. Our aim was to assess predictive performance, feature selection stability, and interpretability under varying sample sizes, feature dimensionality, sparsity patterns, and collinearity levels.

From a practical standpoint, our results suggest tailoring method choice to data characteristics may be warranted. When the number of predictors is small and collinearity is low, stepwise and best subset methods offer good predictive performance and variable selection accuracy, with the added

advantage of interpretability and no need for hyperparameter tuning. In medium-to-large feature spaces or when collinearity is high, regularized methods, particularly Elastic Net and LASSO (1se), provide more stable and parsimonious models. Boruta is especially useful in correlated settings, where its ability to exploit redundancy among predictors yields strong feature selection performance. By contrast, LASSO (min) and SCAD tend to over-select features, sacrificing interpretability and selection accuracy despite competitive raw predictive performance.

Application to the CATALYST study confirmed these patterns. LASSO (min) and Ridge achieved the highest predictive accuracy, while stepwise regression ranked second but yielded a much more parsimonious model. LASSO and stepwise regression largely converged on a core set of predictors for hypercortisolism, whereas Boruta identified additional features that were missed by the linear models.

These findings have important implications. First, they underscore the fact that there is no “one size fits all” model. Classic methods such as stepwise regression demonstrate good predictive power when the feature number is small and feature interaction is low. Regularized methods are more stable under high feature dimensions, but hyperparameter tuning is critical, and small differences in these parameters may lead to very different conclusions and models. Second, our results highlight the value of combining complementary approaches. Methods such as Boruta may reveal alternative or correlated predictors that linear models under-emphasize, offering a broader perspective on potential clinical pathways.

There are several limitations to note. Our simulation settings, while extensive, cannot capture all complexities of real-world datasets. For instance, nonlinear relationships are common in clinical settings, yet our simulation framework was restricted to linear structures. Furthermore, our evaluation emphasized linear modeling strategies, while more flexible approaches such as gradient boosting or neural networks may deliver additional predictive gains, albeit at the expense of interpretability.

In conclusion, this study highlights the practical trade-offs among variable selection methods in clinical research. These insights can help guide the choice of analytic strategy in future discovery and risk prediction efforts, balancing predictive accuracy, model stability, and interpretability in complex clinical populations.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Daniel Einhorn for his thoughtful advice and contributions, which have strengthened this work. The authors are also grateful to Nina Pashova for her support in conducting the analyses. In addition, the authors acknowledge the Corcept biometrics team for their insightful comments and discussions, which improved the clarity and rigor of this work.

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